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North African Transition
to AgroEcology

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NATAE Milestone 7

Compiling Project methodologies

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
AE	Agroecology
AEP	Agroecological practice
AET	Agroecological Transition
ESs	Ecosystem Services
HH	Household
HLPE	High Level Panel of Experts
LL	Living Lab
MDGs	Millennium Development Goals
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
RL	Replication Lab
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TD	Territorial Diagnosis
VC	Value Chain

Executive Summary

This document is a follow up of a first draft for the Methodological Framework for the Assessment of Performance of Agroecological Practices envisaged in the WP1 of the project NATAE (D 1.1 and Ms2) that were developed based on and in interaction with the NATAE Living Lab Guidelines (D4.1) aimed at designing a participative approach adapted to agroecological Living Labs (LL) in North Africa and set up LLs and Replication Labs (RLs) in North African contexts (WP4).

The NATAE's global objective is the development of a methodology to foster agro-ecological transitions in North Africa. During the implementation of the project actions, under the umbrella provided by the D1.1 co-constructed with the partners and the LLs managers, many methodological approaches have been co-developed to deepen knowledge, characterize contexts and, above all, to be able to act effectively by stimulating active bottom-up participation and work together for more sustainable food systems.

This Milestone revolving around the development of a methodology to foster agroecological transitions in North Africa, reports an update of the main methodological aspects in relation to this specific global objective of NATAE, but with specific reference to the construction of a path that led to the identification of the AEPs already present in the territories of the LLs and to the identification of the future development trajectories of AEP practices.

Biodiversity is fundamental to agroecology because it is both a constitutive element of agroecological systems and a strategic resource for their productivity, sustainability and resilience. It supports essential ecosystem functions, such as pollination, biological control of pests and diseases, soil fertility and improves resilience to climatic and biological stresses. A specific part of the compilation is dedicated to the integration of a procedure for participatory assessment of biodiversity in the LLs based on the IUCN Land Health Monitoring Framework through the Guidance Note (Muñoz Cañas, 2025) on monitoring land health in agriculture landscapes.

The path so far has been complex and this Ms7 serves to take stock of what has been built specifically in relation to the multi-actor co-design of optimal AEP combinations. The project path has certainly required many other insights to undertake multi-actor processes based on a shared in-depth knowledge also of the aspects relating to policies, governance of agricultural and food systems, value chains and market dynamics. All these insights that the project is carrying out, in the coming months will flow together and find a synthesis in a path and in a specific approach of the NATAE project to be reported in D1.3 (due by month 48) but are not the subject of this compilation.

Ms7 describes and connects the methodological steps implemented so far in relation to NATAE multiactor co-design of optimal AEP combination for what has been achieved so far.

It aims to report the contributions made by the Consortium towards the achievement of the specific objective 1 (SO1) that are about providing a comprehensive understanding of AE in North Africa, based on the identification of promising AEP combinations and an analysis of their perceptions by key stakeholders.

The results of SO1 are absolutely preliminary and necessary to proceed at full speed with SO2 which deals with the assessment of the multidimensional benefits of AEPs in North Africa, which in turn is considered necessary to take the next step: identifying levers and constraints for the diffusion of AEPs and the conditions, means and tools to support the agroecological transition of African food systems.

This milestone will consider the following NATAE documents:

- D5.3: First multi-actor findings on AEP (combinations) (Van de Ven, 2025)
- Report T4.2: Guide méthodologique Diagnostic d'un territoire rural. Identification des pratiques agroécologiques et analyse de leurs conditions d'adoption (Daoudi, 2023)
- D4.1: NATAE Living Lab guidelines. Version 1.0 (Paas *et al.*, 2023)
- D4.2: Farm household typologies in NATAE Living Labs (Paas *et al.*, 2024)
- D4.5: Strategic options for agroecological transitions (Caulfield *et al.*, 2025)
- Ms3: Methodology to define Living labs boundaries and farm household types. (Belhouchette *et al.*, 2023)
- Ms4: NATAE On multi-actor governance in Living Labs and the MEDAE network. (Paas *et al.*, 2023)

1 Introduction

Researchers agree that AE, considered jointly as a science, a practice and a social movement, should consider the whole food system from the soil to the organization of human societies (Francis, 2003; Therond et al., 2017, Wezel et al., 2018), but how to involve the whole actors of the food system it is still a challenge.

Since the beginning of the Project, the multi-actor activities within NATAE have focused on the identification and on opening possibilities for an iterative self-evaluation of agroecological practices (Ms2) and a conceptual framework has been co-constructed and defined to gradually accompany the Living Labs in these processes (D1.1); combinations of agronomic and socio-economic practices, targeted to different types of farms, and capable of addressing sustainability challenges in food systems are intended as strategic options for agroecological transitions at farm and Living Lab (LL) levels. To identify them, the working group of NATAE Work Package 4 conducted, in collaboration with LL teams and their farmers, three main activities:

- Territorial diagnosis
- Development of a typology of farms
- Workshops with farmers and LL Boards.

Many challenges arise in promoting the agroecological transition at food system level; one of the most difficult that a research project such as NATAE must face, lies in the ability to promote a scientific approach underlying the choice of practices that the LLs communities decide to adopt while considering specific governance options adopted by the LLs; the specific methodological approach adopted by NATAE has been co-constructed in the interaction between researchers and the LLs communities and adapted in operational phase (D5.3).

The analysis for the assessment of biodiversity using the IUCN Land Health Monitoring Framework (Muñoz Cañas, 2025) on monitoring land health in agriculture landscapes in LLs, falls fully within the multiactor approach; this will allow, through the participatory choice of indicators and monitoring at field, farm and landscape levels, to reach shared results, increasing awareness of what the LLs communities can do to conserve the resources of the territories.

The identification of agroecological practices required a specific effort that was carried through in different tasks, starting from T4.2 (Territorial Diagnosis and farming system analysis), to reach the identification of the AEPs reported in D4.5. Chapter 2 of D4.5 reports an effective summary of the work carried out by the Working Group of WP 4 of the NATAE project, which identified strategic options for the agroecological transition in Living Labs (LL) by combining agronomic and socio-organizational practices suitable for different types of farms. The process included three main activities: a territorial diagnosis to analyse contexts and existing practices, the construction of business typologies to capture the diversity of farms (D4.2), and participatory workshops with farmers and local representatives to evaluate and select agroecological practices. The information collected during the process was integrated and shared in a final workshop to define the most promising combinations of practices at farm and territorial level.

In this milestone, a synthetic overview is provided of the main methodological and conceptual steps that have allowed NATAE to reach a matching between the needs and perceptions of stakeholders in the LLs and the AEP practice that the LLs have decided to adopt.

This document consists of the first draft of the NATAE Guidebook (D1.3 due in month 48) and contribute to the compiling of the project methodologies (MS6 due in month 26) of the project. It is structured in three main sections as follow:

1. Multi-actor approach and AEPs
2. Territorial diagnosis and Farm household typologies
3. Agroecological practices
4. Biodiversity

2 Multi-actor approach and AEPs

The methodological approach adopted by the project goes through the creation of a multiactors community (or a number of multiactors communities) in the targeted territories and beyond and this can be achieved adopting the LLs approach; The LLs are by definition, places where innovations are adopted, adapted and new innovations can be co-created in a participatory governance environment, and where participatory methods such as, co-learning, co-design and systems thinking approaches are applied in a transdisciplinary way, and are supposed to be practiced in an iterative way, to dynamically achieve sustainability and resilience.

AEP practices, although many are already in place in the various LLs, are actually innovations that must be subjected to a continuous cycle of improvement and adaptation. Therefore, the working environment of the LLs is ideal for promoting the agroecological transition of the territories.

As a consequence, the project methodologies aimed at building a collaborative working environment that would allow at the same time to arrive at a description and characterization of the contexts and to elicit the vision of local communities in terms of problems, needs and future development trajectories.

The challenges inherent in promoting the agroecological transition for the entire food system are many; one of the most difficult that a research project such as NATAE must face, lies in the ability to promote a scientific approach underlying the choice of practices that the LLs communities decide to adopt, while avoiding a *research driven approach* and promoting a *user driven approach* in the choice of agroecological practices; the methodology adopted so far to achieve this result has been co-constructed in the interaction between researchers (internal and external to the LLs) and the LLs communities and above all in order to adapt to the internal governance of the LLs (D5.3).

D5.3 offers an overview of the tools, working methods and of the participatory approach adopted to mobilize and ensure the involvement of stakeholders in the territories where LLs are present in order to arrive at the identification and then evaluation of agroecological practices in the NATAE LLs 3 The adopted approach involves activities specifically designed at the 7 LLs level¹, networking activities the MEDAE network with an impact at regional level, and the organization of the political conference in Tunis (29-31 January 2025). The application of the IUCN LHMF at the local level is also an example of involving all local actors in a participatory process of analysis of territorial contexts. The approach involves all levels of interest of the LLs, from governance managers to farmers in defining site-specific biodiversity indicators at different levels to evaluate the biodiversity prospects offered by the AEPs. The assessment of the general health status of agricultural landscapes is also facilitated, by including information at soil/field, farm, landscape and national levels.

¹ At the start of the project, six Living Labs were identified by national and external partners with different backgrounds; during the second year one existing Living Lab was replaced, and an additional Living Lab was added for a total of 7 LLs, to whom 3 Replication Labs add.

3 Territorial diagnosis

In the context of our project, and as reported by the methodological document T4.2, a territorial diagnosis is intended to better understand the local context of each of the LL territories to identify existing AE practices, the factors influencing their adoption, and the agricultural and socioeconomic dynamics that influence the choices of local actors. Such analysis helped drawing the evolution and future potential towards a well-ingrained AE transition, thus ultimately linking the contribution of this participative methodology to the overall participatory processes of the project to set up AE strategies at different scales. Task 4.2 Territorial diagnosis and farming system analysis led by ENSA saw the participation of WUR, IAMM and all LLs leaders.

A territory is intended as a geographical space with resources, controlled and reproduced over time by different actors who are not equally positioned within a network of social relations (FAO, 2010) and as a portion of space to which social actors attribute particular social meanings, shared representations and values (Storti *et al.*, 2022). This definition of territory is useful in understanding how social, political, and production and economic processes shape space and the relationships between people and their environment (Storti *et al.*, 2023).

The territorial diagnosis is one of the first steps towards exploring the territories of the LL and generating useful knowledge for the design of the multi-actor process of facilitating the endogenous agroecological transition. The results of the diagnosis are meant to contribute to the identification of scenarios for promoting an endogenic agroecological transition. These scenarios build around specific products, practices and/or processes of production and valorisation of agricultural products, involving actors and stakeholders within the boundaries of the project identified LLs. NATAE project aims to develop a participatory approach through the identified LLs to co-construct a multi-stakeholder process to facilitate the endogenous agroecological transition adapted to each territory.

The implementation of this methodological approach represented one of the participative activities performed in the LLs territories and provided a holistic understanding of the characteristics and dynamics, encompassing a wide range of factors such as socio-economic, environment, infrastructure, agriculture production system and agricultural practices and their relation/contribution to the agroecological transition within the NATAE multidimensional evaluation framework.

The territorial diagnosis carried out under WP4 by the project team in coordination with the LL leadership teams, Representatives Boards and LL farmers is considered as one of the participative activities performed with LLs that served for data collection, analysis, and interpretation to identify key issues and opportunities for the implementation of the NATAE AEP. The territorial diagnosis methodological approach of the analysis (T4.2) and the farm survey (Ms3) aimed at gathering first data to characterize the structure, and the level of environmental and socio-economic assets of the farms' performances.

The TD methodology is detailed in report 4.2 – *Guide méthodologique. Diagnostic d'un territoire rural. Identification des pratiques agroécologiques et analyse de leurs conditions d'adaptation*. The methodology was built on the base of a consultative process internal to the Consortium through the following:

- Definition of the theoretical and methodological framework
- Characterization of the socioeconomic and natural context
- Analysis of agricultural production systems and supply chains

This methodological guide provided simple and operational definitions of the basic concepts necessary for a relevant and targeted characterization of the local food system, its socioeconomic,

technical and environmental determinants, in connection with the agroecological transition. The guide gives a four steps detailed approach (Figure 1) to conducting a rural diagnosis that emphasizes understanding local agricultural dynamics, particularly those engaged in the agroecological transition and/or compatible with it.

Figure 1: The four steps of the proposed territorial diagnosis for the characterization of agroecological practices (Daoudi, 2023)

In conducting such detailed analysis of the LLs, several key elements that reflect the complexity and specificity of each territory were considered that can be referred to three main areas: ecological-biophysical, socioeconomic assets and governance. In particular, the territorial analysis served in all NATAE LLs for the:

1. characterization of the socioeconomic and natural context of the territory by analysing the technical, economic, natural and social factors that explain their existence or absence in local agricultural systems
2. identification of the agroecological practices present in the territory
3. characterization of agricultural production systems with agroecological potential and their value chains (VC) by:
 - 3.1. production useful knowledge to co-construct, with local actors, endogenous and contextualized agroecological transition paths.
 - 3.2. promotion a multi-actor dialogue to discuss and negotiate change options based on local needs and resources.

The characterization of agricultural production systems with agroecological potential and their value chains (VC) aimed to achieve a) a description of the structure and functions of the agricultural production systems, through the characterization of the family group, the means of production (land,

labour, equipment, capital) and animal and plant productions; b) an identification of the farmer objectives and decisions for his choices of means and techniques of production; c) an analysis of the various socioeconomic dynamics through the reconstruction of the history of the production system with the identification of the important events which have determined the current structure of the system to assess the conditions of reproduction of the system over time, in other words its agroecological and socio-economic sustainability; d) an identification of the main VCs in the territory and characterization of VCs compatible with agroecology (activities flows from production to marketing, delineation of the geographical area, institutional framework: policies, regulations, public/private conventions and standards, and characterization of the governance system; stakeholder strategies and power relations that determine the allocation of human and financial resources.

The TD achieved with the collaboration of the local stakeholders and partners involved in the LLs is not only a technical photograph of the territory, but it is a key strategic tool to facilitate the emergence and legitimization of local agroecological trajectories, in dialogue with farmers, technicians, decision makers and other actors in the supply chains.

Some aspects connected with the characterization of LLs and with possibilities for an in deep analysis of territorial contexts were also focused on the framework of other project tasks and reported in specific deliverables. For each of them specific methods and approaches have been co-developed contributing to deepen knowledge, characterizing contexts and defining dynamics of food systems:

- An in-depth study phase on environmental contexts (delineation of agro-ecological zones (AEZs) and analysis of climate and soils) was considered within the deliverable D1.2 Mapping of promising areas for the upscaling of NATAE findings as it was deemed necessary and preliminary to the identification of areas in which to replicate the NATAE findings.
- A complex analysis of the connections between producers, processors, distributors and consumers, including sales channels and market dynamics and the acceptability of AEPs was carried out by the WP3 working group which found a synthesis in the D 3.2¹ Synthesis report on Agroecological Value Chains in North Africa.
- An analytical review of policies related to agriculture and food systems including aspects connected to trade, finance, health and nutrition policies in North African countries have been conducted by WP6 working group with the aim to detect policies the have the potential to foster or hinder AE transition and be able to identify gaps, conflicts and inconsistencies in existing sectoral and inter-sectoral policies (D6.2 Inter-sectoral review of NA policies' strength and weaknesses for an AE transition).

The Territorial Diagnosis results were reported respectively by each LL in a detailed report of all findings (Ms4) and presented and shared among the whole Consortium on the 9th and 12th October 2023 and 10th October 2024 for the new site in Meknes, for Tizi Ouzou and for Siliana..

4 Farm household typologies

After the stock taking phase of the AEPs (D 4.2) it was deemed necessary to understand which are the problems faced by the local stakeholders, which are, among the AEPs already adopted, those that best met the expectations, which instead deserved to be improved and which new practices could

be adopted to face/counter the problems and challenges that limit sustainability and living conditions. Most of the AEPs must be applied by local actors in their own farms, so it was useful to develop a methodology that characterizes the farms of each LLs in order to offer each of them the possibility to choose the practices that best suit the specific case (D4.2).

A mixed approach was applied for the development of the farm typologies as participatory and quantitative methods are considered to be complementary (Alvarez *et al.*, 2018 and Kuivanen *et al.*, 2016). Participatory methods provide contextualisation of typologies, where quantitative methods ensure transparency and reproducibility (Kuivanen *et al.*, 2016). Participatory methods also develop a realistic farm typology recognised and approved by local stakeholders, in contrast to being merely a tool for researchers (Alvarez *et al.*, 2018).

The first data collection and analysis of data in relation to the reference contexts (WP2) was followed by a grouping of the farm typologies present in each LL through the identification of criteria considered decisive in terms of the adoption of agricultural practices (D4.2). The criteria chosen by LLs representatives allow to better adapt the agroecological interventions and practices to the farms and to improve the relevance and scalability of the actions to be developed in the LLs. The farms were grouped into types based on structure (e.g. surface area, crops) and operation (e.g. market orientation).

In the farming system analysis (D4.2), updated or newly built farm typologies appropriate to study the adoption of agroecological practices were identified through participatory workshops. The methodology to achieve specific farm typologies for each of the Living Lab areas is based on a qualitative approach complemented by quantitative data.

In each LL, farm typologies were identified on the basis that they were affected by the same similar production constraints or problems.

The *farm typology* was developed in six phases through the definition of objectives, hypotheses, criteria, data collection, statistical analysis and validation with local actors (4.2). The resulting typologies of household reflect the diversity in terms of structure and functioning of the farms in the LLs. The results show that farm typologies in the NATAE LLs can be described by common characteristics, i.e. crop species, access to credit, off-farm revenues, etc., however, production constraints and farm size specific to farm typologies are very different between LLs and this influences the AEPs, their performance, their adoption and the transferability of AE options and solutions. Biodiversity has not been contemplated among the characterization criteria, so this aspect should receive more attention and be evaluated in subsequent works.

The application of a participatory and multi-inclusive approach has led to obtaining a real vision and knowledge of the current situation and of the opportunities and obstacles that stand in the way of the agroecological transition. The analysis will also allow to produce useful knowledge to co-construct, with local actors, endogenous and contextualized agroecological transition paths and promoted a multi-actor dialogue useful in the subsequent phases of the project to discuss and negotiate options for change based on local needs and resources.

5 Agroecological practices

The methodological steps that allowed us to reach the matching of the AEPs that will be adopted in the LLs, started from the territorial diagnosis and, passing through the identification of the business typologies, laid the foundations for the actual matching work to be done in the LLs.

The previous activities allowed to better understand the local contexts in which LLs are located, to consider the diversity of farming systems the existing already practices AEPs and, in some measure, indication about the potentially adoptable agroecological practices (AEP).

All those information and results were integrated into workshops where LL leaders defined a list of possible AEPs at farm level, finally achieving strategic options.

These AEPs were then discussed in a workshop with farmers. The objective of workshop was to assess the relevance of agroecological practices to farmers' needs and concerns.

During the workshop, a set of AEPs (pre-selected by LL leaders) were discussed. Farmers participated in group discussions and then in a semi-quantitative individual assessment and assigned importance scores to the *areas of concern* and assessed the expected effect of AEPs in relation to them. The areas of concern represented the aspects considered by farmers in the decision-making process about the adoption or non-adoption of each of the practices. The areas of concern were: water, soil, microclimate, biodiversity, pest and disease, animal welfare, labour, productivity, Consumption/processing, costs, revenue/income, collective organisation, Others. The combined results for each area of concern provided a score for each practice. In a second step farmers were asked to provide a score for each expected effect of each single AEP on the areas of concern. The scores for each area of concern were multiplied and combined into a practice score per practice and per area of concern. This allowed a comparison of the practices providing a base for discussion, knowledge sharing and choice as the scores were discussed collectively.

The results of the farmers' workshop were brought to the attention of the Representative Board during a subsequent workshop, which aimed to identify and find solutions to the barriers to the adoption of AEPs identified by farmers. Common barriers (e.g. access to resources, training, market) were discussed and explored by identifying, and grouping by intervention sectors, the solutions that can be implemented at LL level (e.g. seed banks, cooperatives, training). Then the board members selected the most relevant and most feasible options and a list of AEPs at LL level was created including practices of socio-political and organisational type.

The workshop was held with the purpose of identify strategic options for the agroecological transition. It aimed to integrate all the information to map the most suitable AEPs for the different types of farms, and to identify the socio-organizational levers at LL level to promote their diffusion. in the workshop the LL leaders analysed the AEPs in relation to the farm types. then the barriers and levers for each farm type were identified and finally a matrix was generated showing the combinations between AEPs at farm and LL level that appear most promising for the agroecological transition.

The matching and identification of AEPs at the level of each single LL were achieved thanks to workshops in which LL leaders and farmers made a series of shared and responsible choices based on raised common awareness. Each list of AEPs combinations for each LL achieved in the final workshop, constitutes the strategic options for each LL to achieve the agroecological transition of the territory.

6 Biodiversity

The agroecological approach and the possibility of moving towards an agroecological transition of a territory is based on the capacity to support production offered by the agroecosystem; the performance of agroecological practices is closely connected to the capacity of agroecosystems to perform ecosystem functions and provide ecosystem services, especially those most immediately perceived by stakeholders as relevant for agricultural activity and the food system (nutrient cycling, pest and disease regulation, contrast to soil erosion and depletion, water purification,...). The provision of most ecosystem services depends on biodiversity, that is the natural capital existing in territorial contexts which defines their state of health. This entails that to promote and achieve an agroecological transition it is necessary to define multifunctional agricultural systems that respond to the maintenance of biodiversity by aiming at the protection of plants from adversity, at improving the fertility of the soil, the integration of herbaceous crops with trees, of cultivated areas with non-cultivated ones, and at the integration of crops with livestock (Altieri et al., 2003).

In such farm management systems, synergies are stimulated to support yields, exploiting internal resources by means of the nutrient cycling and of the organic matter, and by promoting trophic relationships between plants and insects that favour the biological control of harmful organisms.

In such agricultural systems (or agroecosystems) biodiversity is not just the direct expression and the term of evaluation of the state of conservation and health of an environmental system, but biodiversity expresses system's productivity, stability and the ability of being self-supporting and self-perpetuating in the long run.

Biodiversity of agricultural areas includes 1) species used directly or indirectly for food and agriculture, both for human nutrition and as feed for domestic animals, and the provision of essential raw materials and services such as fibre, fertilizer, fuel and pharmaceuticals; 2) habitats and species outside of the farming systems which can benefit agriculture and enhance ecosystem functions.

It covers, inter alia belowground and aboveground organisms as crop varieties (including forage and fodder plants and trees) animal species (including fish, molluscs, bird species and insects) as well as fungi, yeasts and micro-organisms.

Agricultural biodiversity is actively managed by farmers. Many components of agricultural biodiversity would not survive without this human interference and indigenous knowledge and culture are integral parts of agricultural biodiversity management.

Because of the degree of human management, conservation of agricultural biodiversity in production systems is inherently linked to sustainable use – preservation of medicinal and aromatic species through protected areas is relevant.

Since 1995, Vandermeer (1995) suggested that biodiversity in agroecosystems has two components, planned and associated.

Planned biodiversity is the portion of biodiversity consisting of cultivated crops, livestock, and associated organisms (such as agents of biological control) that are purposely included in an agroecosystem for direct economic benefit. It is normally managed more or less intensively to produce high yields.

Associated biodiversity includes all the plants, herbivores, carnivores, and microbes that pre-exist in or immigrate into the agroecosystem from surrounding habitats. Associated biodiversity persists to a greater or lesser degree within an agroecosystem depending on whether the ecological requirements of each organism of the community are met.

By proposing agricultural practices for the agroecological transition we move at the interface between the planned and associated components that coexist and must work together in order to provide the ecosystem services that are essential to sustainably conduct agricultural activity.

Biodiversity and AEPs in LLs

Farmers are those who act and transform the territories, it is therefore important to understand the perception of biodiversity and the health of agroecosystems by farmers and stakeholders of LLs because having an idea of how this element is understood and valued and how this changes over time in relation to the different moments of development of the project, can provide a useful benchmark of the methodological approach adopted; a better understanding of the reasons behind the changes in their mind set and in the behaviours of local communities that occur following their involvement in project activities, would allow for greater effectiveness of future actions (Taplin et al., 2013).

From D4.5 much can be guessed about farmers mind set about biodiversity. The process of identifying the AEPs is the result of the joint work between researchers, LLs leaders and the different communities of actors who participated in the meetings, and it is possible to understand the perception of the relevance of biodiversity at the level of the different LLs. Biodiversity was included as an area of concern in the farmer workshops (D4.5), so farmers were able to express their opinion on its relevance in general and also their idea on the impact of the agricultural practices considered on biodiversity. They then chose the AEPs to adopt in the companies based on the areas of concern most relevant to them. Downstream of the process, it is possible to detect from the values assigned by them what their idea is on biodiversity and what their perception is of the effects of the practices on biodiversity.

From D 4.5 the perception of relevance of biodiversity and of the potential impact of AEPs on it varies significantly among the LLs. From a reading of the tables summarizing the selection process of the AEPs, a higher attention to biodiversity is found in the LLs of Tizi Ouzou, Laghouat, Luxor and in the LL PK-17, a very low perception of impact of AEPs is found in Skoura M'Daz, in Siliana, and in Ait Othmane.

In LL PK-17 (Mauritania) biodiversity is not perceived and mentioned among the benefits that can be derived from the adoption of AEPs, but farmers considered or observed very high the effect of the practices on biodiversity. The focus is on water management, nutritional fertility and productivity.

In the LL of Luxor / El Boghdady (Egypt) although it is not mentioned among the advantages identified by farmers in relation to AEP, biodiversity is mentioned among the five themes considered a priority for farmers. Among the AEP that they propose to adopt, the need to use salinity resistant varieties is reported; therefore, the perception of the relevance of biodiversity is suggested by the need to adapt the varietal choice to the salinity problems that have arisen.

The LL of Tizi Ouzou (Algeria) is one of the two LLs in which biodiversity was explicitly mentioned as an element of interest by the participants; biodiversity is mentioned as one of the benefits/advantages that derive from the application of manure because it attracts useful fauna (earthworms...) and increases the percentage of germination (vegetable and aromatic medicinal plants). Furthermore, although the LLs did not include the application of manure among the practices to be promoted, it did identify the use of local seeds as a relevant agroecological practice, and this is a practice directly linked to the conservation and safeguarding of local agricultural genetic diversity.

In the LL of Laghouat during the workshop with farmers, biodiversity was explicitly mentioned among the advantages deriving from the practice of introducing prickly pears in the farms and using nettle porridge, while very low value is given to data pollinators. As in the case of the other LLs, biodiversity was not included among the criteria for choosing the farmers although much attention was paid to

Soil Health. The choice of the AEPs to use prickly pears as windbreak hedges (prickly pear), to use natural pesticides based on nettles and to improve the composting techniques of which they recognize the positive effects on the microbial activity of the soil leave us to hope that in the future they will be able to appreciate the advantages of the associated biodiversity.

In this regard, it should be noted that biodiversity has not been formally included among the main criteria for characterizing the territories of the Living Labs (T 4.2 Territorial Diagnosis and Farming System Analysis) nor among the criteria for characterizing the types of farms (D4.2), however, in the territorial report of the Living Lab of Laghouat and El Assafia (Algeria) biodiversity is mentioned. The community of the LL of Laghouat recognizes its importance as a lever for the agroecological transition. In the same LL, agricultural practices aimed at conserving and enhancing local agrobiodiversity are currently being implemented to counteract the risk of disappearance of local seeds and seedlings; farmers attribute the ever-decreasing availability of seeds of local varieties to progressive urbanization. Some AEPs to counter genetic erosion are already being practiced for date palms and some native varieties; there is a certain emphasis on the management of local seeds and plants, even if “timidly practiced” because it would require a significant allocation of work efforts and resources. In the LL of Laghouat the adoption of agroecological practices is considered an opportunity because it could favour crop and varietal diversity, the integration between agriculture and livestock, the reduced use of chemical inputs, and the regeneration of local ecosystems. At the moment a certain effort is dedicated to the practice of protection and promotion of local animal breeds, coupled/joined with the valorisation of the practice of seasonal transhumance of sheep flocks.

In the LL of Siliana (Tunisia) biodiversity is among the areas of interest that have achieved the lowest vote from farmers. Their choices mainly addressed to soil health have however included among the practices to be promoted in the LL crop rotations, intercropping, and no-till sowing, which could have important positive effects on soil biodiversity.

In the LL of Ait Othmane/Meknes (Morocco), although biodiversity is not included among the areas of concern, biodiversity is mentioned among the benefits that derive from the adoption of drip irrigation systems, speaking that they would help maintain supportive species in the agricultural ecosystem, but the score assigned is 0. The AEPs chosen concerns the use of manure, rotations and crop associations and composting, all practices that could favour an increase in associated biodiversity.

In the LL of Skoura M'Daz (Morocco) the perception of the impact of AEPs on biodiversity has received a very low value. At the same time, the report states that among the advantages of MAP cultivation there is an observed effectiveness in reducing the incidence of pests and diseases for olive trees and also the idea of using MAPs to carry out treatments for the control of adversities. The connection between AEPs and MAPs and biodiversity is a bit missing in the perception of the players. However, the proposed AEP practices such as composting, windbreak hedges and associated crops suggest a potentially positive appreciation of the increase of biodiversity.

In the territorial context of Skoura the value of spontaneous plants for rural development processes is well recognized, and some initiatives of significant social value are based precisely on the presence of spontaneous Aromatic and Medicinal Plants in the territory. For example, a cooperative (Najah) managed by women that makes plant extracts from spontaneously collected plants is located and operates in a protected area of the Middle Atlas, and as such is also committed to ensuring the protection and conservation of endemic and protected species in agreement with the Park management authority and local authorities; another example is the Safirate Alaachab cooperative located in Skoura and born from the initiative of 6 women who, after having acquired experience in extracting essences from spontaneous aromatic and medicinal plants, decided to cultivate them to support the production and sale of products, becoming entrepreneurs themselves; they have activated a small processing company for the extraction of essences and also a sales office. However, although in this LL the mainly spontaneous medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) have a fundamental

importance as a source of income and a factor of local development, there is no awareness of the fact that they are part of the associated biodiversity and natural capital of the places and as such can be positively or negatively impacted by farm practices. Greater awareness would lead to triggering AEPs specifically aimed at its protection and sustainable use.

From the analysis of the project report of T4.2, D4.2 and D4.5 it is clear that the word biodiversity in the perception of farmers has a partial meaning and, in some cases, it is connected to the planned agricultural biodiversity (local varieties, resistant, breeds, ...).

Although in some cases (e.g. in the case of aromatic and medicinal plants) the value of individual species for local rural development processes or for the ability to counter adversities is recognized, the value of biodiversity as "natural capital" is not yet well understood. A participatory monitoring action could change this state of things leading to the recognition of the value of biodiversity as natural capital capable of generating many ecosystem services useful to agricultural contexts, a greater level of collective awareness could really increase the resilience of local communities.

6.1 Assessing and monitoring biodiversity and natural capital

The adoption and diffusion of agroecological practices at the level of NATAE LLs opens a concrete possibility to integrate biodiversity monitoring in the reference territories through the IUCN Land Health Monitoring Framework and the IUCN Guidance Note (Muñoz Cañas, 2025) on monitoring land health in agriculture landscapes.

The Land Health is the capacity of land, relative to its potential, to sustain delivery of ecosystem services (Shepherd et al., 2015) and the *Land Health Monitoring Framework* provides ways for monitoring biodiversity at different levels in productive agroecosystems.

The Land Health Monitoring Framework (LHMF), initially designed to assess the positive impacts on biodiversity of IUCN projects, is a comprehensive tool designed to support biodiversity monitoring in different contexts and in relation to actions and practices that are designed and implemented to promote positive change, such as the transition from conventional to sustainable and agroecological agriculture, agricultural landscape restoration and/or ecosystem restoration actions and Nature Based Solutions (NBS) implementations. The LHMF allows and guides towards the integration of a wide range of tools, parameters and indices, ensuring a holistic assessment of the state of health of the land at all scales. The IUCN framework allows for the selection of appropriate indicators for biodiversity monitoring at four levels of analysis: field, farm, landscape and national/global with an emphasis on the environmental pillar of sustainability, focusing on biodiversity and the state of natural resources.

The IUCN LHMF aims to assess biodiversity at four interconnected levels to provide a comprehensive understanding of ecosystem dynamics:

Field/Soil Level: Assessing soil biotic structure, including belowground biodiversity such as microorganisms, fungi, and invertebrates.

Farm Level: Evaluating the impact of farming practices on biodiversity, including the aboveground biodiversity such as domestic/wild animals and plants in an agricultural production unit and as well as in the surroundings.

Landscape Level: Measuring ecosystem functions across agricultural landscapes, the biodiversity that is not considered in the other two levels (farm and field) and the diversity of habitats in a predefined geographical area.

This approach is what NATAE proposes to guide Living Labs towards a greater focus on biodiversity and to ensure that biodiversity conservation remains a key component of agricultural transformation. The guide enables, in this case, NATAE Living Lab partners to:

1. Select appropriate Biodiversity Indicators at different scales (field, farm, landscape and national) to monitor ecosystem functions and biodiversity trends.
2. Engage stakeholders and promote collaboration between farmers, cooperatives, policy makers and researchers to define biodiversity indicators and implement monitoring methods and protocols.
3. Collect and analyse relevant data through available tools and indicators in order to assess biodiversity and ecosystem services.
4. Adapt biodiversity monitoring needs to local conditions by adopting context-specific approaches that ensure that monitoring is aligned with local climate conditions, agricultural practices and socio-economic realities.
5. To facilitate the process of involving LLs in the assessment and monitoring work, IUCN has conducted an initial analysis aimed at facilitating the choice of indicators, based on the results of the territorial analysis of each LL and on the types of farms (D 4.2), allowing the identification of the most relevant functional biodiversity indicators for specific contexts in the seven LLs.

The use of the LHM (Land Health Monitoring Framework) and the IUCN Guidelines will serve for structured biodiversity assessments, while ensuring alignment with the Multidimensional Multiscale Assessment Framework D1.1 (Calabrese et al. 2023); stakeholder engagement will lead to strengthened collaboration between farmers, researchers and policy makers to agree on biodiversity indicators and Agroecological Effectiveness Plans (AEP); conducting continuous biodiversity assessments will allow to refine methodologies and adapt AEP adoption strategies in an iterative process.

Figure 2: Biodiversity and agroecological practices in NATAE (Requier-Desjardins).

This activity will allow to develop replicable monitoring models and to extend biodiversity monitoring and agroecological transitions beyond the initial Living Labs.

IUCN is currently actively reaching out to key local stakeholders in the LLs to be actively involved in the co-selection of indicators and in understanding their connection with the agroecological practices that have been selected for adoption. The first meetings with the LLs Morocco and Tunisia have given positive feedback regarding the willingness to choose the specific indicators to adopt the LHMF. The LLs leaders immediately understood the relevance of contributing and activating a monitoring of natural capital, and the state of health of agroecosystems. The idea is that this participatory exercise implemented with the involvement of farmers activates a process of social valuation that further sensitizes local actors on the value of biodiversity understood as natural capital and, on the need, to increase the provision of ecosystem services to support the agroecological transition and improve the economic performance of AEPs.

The application of the IUCN LHMF and the IUCN Guidance Notes allows to define site-specific biodiversity indicators at different levels to evaluate the biodiversity prospects opened by the AEPs. Furthermore, the assessment of the general state of health of agricultural landscapes is facilitated, by entering information at soil/field, farm, landscape and national levels. Currently, in the various Living Labs, the participatory selection of biodiversity indicators is being carried out with the joint work of IUCN and the LLs referents and will proceed to reach a first detailed analysis to identify the functional biodiversity indicators most relevant for their specific contexts and for the further involvement of the main local stakeholders – farmers, researchers and policy makers – in the critical analysis of the results and in the process of selecting and refining the sets of indicators.

The participatory approach adopted to promote the biodiversity monitoring action will be an important moment both for the exchange of knowledge between partners and with LLs, and will raise awareness on the meaning and functions and importance of associated biodiversity for agroecosystems and for the resilience of local populations.

A further step towards the agroecological transition and for the achievement of long-term sustainability will be achieved when it will be clear how these indicators are related to the selected agroecological practices and to the achievement of an effective balance between agricultural productivity and safeguarding the health of ecosystems. The participatory approach will allow the exchange of knowledge and will strengthen the practical adoption of AEPs that can, on the basis of their effect also on biodiversity, lead associated biodiversity to be considered among the areas of concern because farmers and local players in the LL will be aware that biodiversity is not just the direct expression and/or the term of evaluation of the state health of an environmental system, but biodiversity expresses system's productivity, stability and the ability of being self-supporting and self-perpetuating in the long run.

6.2 Biodiversity, multi-actor co-design of optimal AEPs combinations through adoption of models for the creation of potential scenarios (SO2)

In the next project phases, the multi-actor co-design of optimal AEPs combinations will be enriched by the results of biodiversity assessments at territorial level coming from the application of the LHMF. The experience and enrichment of knowledge and experiences that will derive from the participatory approach foreseen by the NATAE and the participation in the applying the LHMF with IUCN Team will raise awareness on the value of biodiversity for the agroecological transition of the farming systems in LLs communities. This experience will strengthen common knowledge and will pave the way for the subsequent co-design phase of the AEP combinations in which the knowledge deriving from the analysis of policies and governance systems of food systems and value chains and markets will be integrated by adopting integrated modelling chain approaches and will shed lights on additional

aspects relevant for the transition towards more sustainable food systems. The project is finalizing the creation of modelling tools that will help to identify combinations of AEPs suitable for the different needs of the LLs, in order to make it possible to create different scenarios based on the strategic choices that the stakeholders will make. The DAHBSIM model is an example of an integrated modelling approach that combines biophysical, bioeconomic indicators at regional and farm scales in a modelling chain. It will be used to develop a unique integrated assessment of agricultural systems, aimed at assessing the resilience of agricultural systems based on the combinations of AEPs chosen by the LLs.

In the framework of the WP6 activities, ZALF works on the integration of biodiversity as a *core simulation parameter* within the Value Chain module of the DAHBSIM model (Tasks 6.2 and 6.3) in order to provide a scenario analysis suitable for assessing the impacts and performances of biodiversity policies in relation to AEPs performances in varied contexts.

When these results will have the possibility to guide the development of local or national policy options, we will hopefully be able to extend this development model to the whole region

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